

Review of Lean Manufacturing Philosophy in Manufacturing SMEs to Identify Critical Success Factors

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Abstract: Most of the manufacturing industries have been facing challenges of rapidly changing set of market requirements and demand. For developing countries such as Indian manufacturing industries to stay in competition and maintain their market share in this global market, the adaptation of lean manufacturing system has become essential. Lean Manufacturing focus on the systematic elimination of waste and non-value added activity from the production process, reduce time and cost for improved operational and financial performance. Although many firms are attempting to implement lean, only an estimated very few percent are achieving the desired level of success. The comprehensive literature review method has been adopted for the study. This study will provide current status of Lean Manufacturing principle and accompany the organization to prepare framework to identify the critical success factors (CSF) that constitute a successful implementation of lean Manufacturing within manufacturing small and medium enterprise (SMEs).

Keywords: Lean Manufacturing (LM), Critical success factors (CSF), Manufacturing industry, Small and medium enterprises (SMEs), Developing countries

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Lean Manufacturing Overview

Lean manufacturing concepts were developed over the last five to six decades, primarily in Japan, particularly for the Toyota production system. Lean manufacturing revolutionizes the manufacturing process (Jain and Malik, 2013). Lean manufacturing is a systematic approach for eliminating any type of waste from manufacturing operations (Salonitis and Tsinopoulos, 2016). These wastes are defined as waste or muda of Lean: T—

Transport—moving people, products, and information; I—Inventory—storing parts, pieces, documentation ahead of requirements; M—Motion—bending, turning, reaching, lifting; W—Waiting—for parts, information, instructions, equipment; O—Overproduction—making more than is IMMEDIATELY required; O—Over-processing—tighter tolerances or higher grade materials than are necessary; D—Defects—rework, scrap, incorrect documentation (Roberta S. Russell, Bernard W. Taylor III, 2011, Operations Management, John Wiley and Sons, Inc). Lean Manufacturing forms house as shown in fig. 1

Fig. 1. House of Lean (Jones DT and Womack J., 1996)

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Literature review has been carried out by comprehensively studying research papers and case studies published in various international journals from prominent publishers

Elsevier, Emerald, Taylor and Francis, Springer to name a few. Brief description of research work carried out by researchers till now in the field of Lean Manufacturing is furnished as follows:

TABLE 1: Literature review on Lean Manufacturing philosophy

Sr. No.	Authors	Year	Main Findings & Critical Success Factors
1	Salonitis and Tsinopoulosb	2016	<p>The analysis of the questionnaires developed revealed the level of understanding, the key barriers and drivers behind lean implementation success.</p> <p>CSF: Organizational culture and ownership, Developing organizational readiness, Management commitment and capability, Providing adequate resources to support change, External support from consultants in the first instance, Effective communication and engagement, Strategic approach to improvements, Teamwork and joined-up whole systems thinking, Timing to set realistic timescales for change and to make effective use of commitments and enthusiasm for change</p> <p>Barriers: Top management related barriers(Poor commitment from top because of poor knowledge/ understanding, poor belief on the approach/ advantage, change inertia, top management commitment lasted too shortly), Financial barriers (Necessity of high investment/ cost), Workforce related barriers (Employee's fear of job cutting, change inertia, change was not shared, poor knowledge / understanding), Other barriers (Distractions/ slow down due to fire fighting on other project / problems, multiple production sites, difficulty in quantifying the benefits upfront.</p>
2	Sisson and Elshennawy	2015	<p>The final, tested model can provide companies wishing to implement lean with a framework for implementation.</p> <p>Key Factors: Deployment, Engagement, Training, processes, Drivers, Culture</p>
3	Achanga et al.	2006	<p>CSF: Leadership and management, Financial capabilities, Skills and expertise, Organizational culture</p>
4	Netland	2015	<p>To succeed with implementing a lean program in a factory, managers must commit to and involve themselves in the activities of implementation. Such active leadership must be sustained – and even intensified – as implementation progresses. Developing lean knowledge and competency by offering continual education and training to both managers and employees is critical for success. External resources can be used early on, but they will have a more limited effect when plants reach higher implementation stages. Furthermore, there is a persistent need for proper planning, following-up and funding of the lean program. In the early stages of implementation, sharing best practices and establishing a dedicated implementation team can be effective. As implementation progresses, these factors become less important and managers should plant-wide routines by increasing the empowerment of shop floor employees.</p> <p>CSF: Management commitment and involvement, Training and education, Employee participation and empowerment, Alignment to strategy and long term plan, Managing cultural change, Supplier involvement, Customer involvement, Teamwork, Process management, Structured approach and</p>

Sr. No.	Authors	Year	Main Findings & Critical Success Factors
			project prioritizing, Benchmarking and knowledge transfer, Cross functional integration, Quality data and analysis, Project management skills, Performance measurement, Organization infrastructure, Sustain continuous improvement, Quality control and robust process, Use of tools, techniques and technologies, Communication, Reward and recognition, Job security and social responsibility
5	Hibadullah et al.	2014	CSF: Supplier management, Employee involvement, Just in time, Customer focus, Statistical process control
6	Dora et al.	2015	Determinant Factors: Commitment of top management, Culture, Piecemeal approach, Training, Multifunctional team, Resource, Organizational structure, Remuneration, Change agent, Nature of the process, Nature of product, Nature of the plant
7	Sangwan et al.	2014	<p>The study identified 12 drivers for the LM implementation in Indian ceramic industry. Further, these 12 drivers have been categorized into internal, policy and external drivers (ED). Structural model affirms that ED are positively related to policy drivers (PD) and PD are positively related to internal drivers.</p> <p>Drivers: High level of stock/inventory, Low manpower productivity, Poor skills/capabilities of workers, Unavailability of skilled workers, High labor cost, High scrap/rework/rejection, Poor commitment of employees, Customer wants reliable and prompt deliveries, Fluctuating customer orders, High product variety/ customer specific products, Unbalanced workload on different workstation, Poor workplace organization and housekeeping, High cost of energy (electricity or fuel cost), Weak process control, Low capacity to fulfill the regular demand of customers, Lack of standard operating procedures, Short time to fulfill customer orders, Low quality material or parts by suppliers, Suppliers take long time to deliver, Frequent changes in supply schedule by customers</p>
8	Patri and Suresh	2017	<p>The study suggests that leadership is the most crucial factor for lean implementation success and availability of adequate training, acts as a catalyst.</p> <p>CSF: Lean leadership, Frontline workforce engagement, Inter departmental co-operation, Lean training, Time commitment for lean implementation, Professional culture, Notion of inappropriateness of lean system in healthcare, Notion of lean implementation as cost cutting and layoffs, Goal specificity, Healthcare organizational resistance</p>
9	Azyan, Pulakanam, Pons	2017	Success Factors: Strategic need, Organizational size, Leadership, Management commitment, Finance, Organizational culture, Employee participation, Skills and expertise, Tools and Methods
10	Elnadi and Shehab	2015	Enablers: Supplier relationship, Management quality, Employee quality, Work process, Management status, Customer relationship
11	Jie Ma Zhibin Lin Chi Keung Lau	2017	<p>The results of the study indicate that Personnel factor enablers are the most important factor for Kaizen, whilst Software factor enablers (essential rules, policies and institutional arrangements) weight second and Hardware factor enablers (physical, measurable hard facts or resources) weight last. The study also reviews that Kaizen is the most selected improvement method among the three.</p> <p>Enablers: The hardware factor enabler, (Monetary investment, Technologies, Machinery equipment, Experts/ Consultant), The software factor enabler (Training / Job rotation, Open communication, Incentives / Rewards, Standard</p>

Sr. No.	Authors	Year	Main Findings & Critical Success Factors
			procedures, Improvement culture, Improvement system, Benchmarking / feedback, Shop floor management), The personnel factor enabler (Top managers, Middle managers, Line managers, Shop floor personnel, Non production personnel)
12	Noori	2015	CSF: Strategic orientation and leadership infrastructure, Culture, Management system, Implementation process, Implementation team
13	Stone	2012	Factors: Leanness, Transformational, External environment, Mission and strategy, Leadership, Culture, Performance, transactional, structure, management practices, System, Climate, Task / skill, Motivation, Need and values
14	Sim and Rogers	2008	Results from the survey show that the problem lies primarily with an aging and high seniority hourly workforce and a lack of committed leadership at this research site. For example, salaried employees consistently provided higher positive ratings of CI initiatives. In addition, higher seniority was directly correlated with negative ratings. Finally, the study found that employees do not feel valued when they contribute to the improvement processes and that 100 per cent of the hourly male employees disagreed that “The Company considers the employees as the most important asset and will do whatever they can to keep their people”. Managerial implications
15	Shang and Pheng	2014	Barriers: Lack of long term philosophy, Absence of lean culture in the organization, Limited use of D&B procurement mode, Construction firm’s limited involvement in the design, Insufficient knowledge of lean, Multi-layer subcontracting, Limited use of site construction technique, Insufficient management skills, Lack of support from top management, High turnover of workforce, Insufficient training, Employee and management resistance to change, Employee tolerance of untidy workplace, Absence of lean culture in partners, Inadequate delivery performance, Hierarchies in organizational structure, Less personnel empowerment, Avoid making decisions and taking responsibility, Using guanxi or relationships to conceal mistakes, Stringent requirements and approvals, Lack of support from government
16	Jadhav et al.	2014	Barriers: Top management resistance, Lack of top/senior management focus, leadership, Lack of top/senior management involvement (commitment and support), Lack of communication between management and workers, Lack of empowerment of employees, Workers’ resistance, Lack of perseverance, Lack of consultants and trainers in the field, Lack of formal training for managers, Lack of formal training for workers, Cultural difference, Lack of cooperation and mutual trust between management and employees, Cross-functional conflicts, Incompatibility of lean with the company bonus, rewards or incentives systems, The lack of resources to invest, Slow response to market, Lack of information sharing or communication with suppliers and customers, Lack of cooperation from suppliers, Lack of influence over suppliers or lack of involvement of suppliers in the actual implementation, Lack of supplier collaboration or lack of mutually beneficial strategic partnership with suppliers and customers (supply chain members), Quality problems with supplied material, Absence of a sound strategic action/logistical planning system, Lack of logistic support, Problems with machines and plant configuration
17	Amir H. Abolhassani Ky Layfield Bhaskaran	2016	Implementation Difficulties: Sample demographics, Facilities’ size and years of lean strategic practice, Most Beneficial and least difficult lean strategic

Sr. No.	Authors	Year	Main Findings & Critical Success Factors
	Gopalakrishnan		practiced, Level of implementation for the most beneficial lean strategic practices, Difficulties for implementing lean strategic practices, Difficulties of implementing lean for practitioners, Difficulties for implementing lean of non-practitioners
18	Lodgaard et al.	2016	Barriers: Management, Knowledge, Organizing for lean, Use of tools and practices
19	Dora et al.	2013	CSF: Leadership and management, Organizational culture, Skill of the workforce and in-house expertise, Financial capabilities
20	Bortolotti et al.	2014	Culture dimensions: Power distance, institutional collectivism, In-group collectivism, Future orientation, Performance orientation, Gender egalitarianism, Assertiveness, Uncertainty avoidance, Humane orientation
21	Marodin and Saurin	2017	<p>The main contribution of this study is the framework for managing barriers to LPI, which consists of normative theory for LPI. Such type of theory refers to the development of guidance about what actions will and will not lead to the desired result. The proposed guidance refers to the steps to identify, analyze the relationships, prioritize and control barriers to LPI, taking into account the role of context. Data analysis also allowed the emergence of a meta-prescription, namely that the process of LPI, and thus the management of barriers, should adopt lean principles.</p> <p>Barriers: People seem demotivated after a few years, Lack of human and / or financial resources, Difficulties in seeing the financial problems, middle management not giving enough support, Top management not giving enough support, Lack of support on the shop floor, Operators are insecure in carrying out new attributions, Operators are afraid of lay off due to improvements, The operators do not feel responsible for using lean practices and solving problems, Managers lack technical knowledge and skill to guide the LPI, Not sustaining the improvements in the medium and long term, Having difficulties to keep the pace of the ongoing LPI activities.</p>
22	Bhasin	2012	<p>Obstacles: Culture, Past history of initiatives, Staff attitudes, operative resistance, Unique of lean journey, View lean as long term journey, Lean not synonymous to lean tools, Lean applied to the value chain, Cost of implementation, Measuring the benefits of lean, View lean as business proposition, Traditional cost accounting system, Internal communication system,</p> <p>Backsliding to old methods. Insufficient supervisory skills to implement lean, Employee attitudes/resistance to change, Insufficient workforce skills to implement lean Insufficient senior management skills to implement lean Insufficient management time, Cultural issues, Cost of the investment, Insufficient understanding of the potential benefits, Insufficient internal funding, Insufficient external funding, A need to convince shareholders / owners</p>
23	Rane et al.	2016	<p>Barrier: Health issue, Lack of multitasking, Leadership and management, Monotony, Communication, Resistance toward lean implementation, cultural differences</p> <p>Enabler: Top management support, Shared vision, Expertise, Transparency, Predictability</p> <p>Driver: Knowledge, Can do attitude, Compensation, Education and training,</p>

Sr. No.	Authors	Year	Main Findings & Critical Success Factors
			Empowerment, Employee involvement, Competitor, Trust, Motivation, Teamwork
24	Losonci et al.	2011	Factors: Lean success, Commitment (Feeling of involvement), Belief, Work method, Communication
25	Singh et al.	2012	<p>Customers issues: To reduce response time, To deliver in small lots, To implement self-certification, To reduce rejection, To increase range of products</p> <p>Organizational issues: Frequent breakdown, High inventory, High rejection rate, Underutilization of capacity, Workers absenteeism, Obsolete technology, High setup time/changeover time</p> <p>Supplier issues: Unreliable transport, Frequent changes in supply schedule, Poor communication system, Poor vendor response, Frequent design changes, High lead time, Market issues, Stiff competition, Low sales revenue, Poor brand image</p> <p>Top management issues: Lack of funds, Lack of multi-skilled manpower, Lack of quality consciousness, Lack of support from top management</p>
26	Taj	2008	Factors: Inventory, Team approach, Process, Maintenance, Layout and handling, Supplier, Setup, Quality, Scheduling / Control
27	Naga Vamsi Krishna Jasti Rambabu Kodali	2016	The major constraints to implement LM principles were employee resistance and lack of awareness about LM principles among industry professionals. The study also revealed that majority of the organizations have implemented in specific area of the manufacturing operation with very few popular tools of LM instead of following any systematic approach to implementing LM principles across whole organization.
28	Almanei, Salontis, Xu	2017	<p>CSF: Top management, Training and education, Thinking development, Employees, Working culture, Communication, Resources, Customer focus, Government intervention</p> <p>Challenges: Organizational culture and ownership, Developing organizational readiness, Management commitment and capability, Providing adequate resources to support change, External support from consultants in the first instance, Effective communication and engagement, Strategic approach to improvements, Teamwork and joined-up whole systems thinking, Timing to set realistic timescales for change and to make, effective use of commitments and enthusiasm for change</p>
29	Anna Dorota Rymaszewska	2014	Challenges: The challenge of long-term orientation, The challenge of becoming a learning organization, The challenge of leveling out workflow, The challenge of supplier-buyer relations and JIT, The challenge of employee empowerment and standardization of the work procedures
30	Kumar and Antony	2008	<p>Differences in quality management practices such as customer focused measures and method of knowledge transfer to employees, were observed in Six Sigma and ISO certified SMEs. The main reasons cited for not implementing Six Sigma in SMEs were lack of knowledge or understanding of the system and limited resources. A significant difference in the performance of Six Sigma/lean firms against ISO certified companies were observed with respect to the strategic and operational measures of organizational performance</p> <p>CSF: Management involvement, Communication, Link QI to employee, Cultural change, Education and training, Link QI to customer, Project</p>

Sr. No.	Authors	Year	Main Findings & Critical Success Factors
			selection, Link QI to business, Link QI to supplier, project selection, Link QI to business, Link QI to supplier, project management skill, Organization infrastructure, Vision and plan, It and innovation Barriers: availability of resources, Lack of knowledge, Lack of training, Internal resistance, Poor employee participation, Inadequate process control technique, Changing business focus, Lack of management commitment, Poor delegation authority, Poor supplier involvement, Poor project selection
31	Garcia et al.	2013	CSF: Commitment and motivation of staff Support from senior management, Allocated resources (time, economic, spaces), Leadership, Developing culture of continuous improvement, Set goals for improvement programs, Using an appropriate methodology, Standardization and process measurement, Organization of support teams, Presence of a facilitator to support the program, Interdepartmental communication, Differences between the focus of improvement and the existing culture, Employee attitude, Interdepartmental cooperation, Follow the PDCA cycle, Training and education, Heterogeneity of improvement teams, Assessment system, Skills and experience, Establish policies, objectives and structure, Clarify goals and common ideas
32	Shaaban and Awani	2014	CSF: Leadership style and influence, Management commitment, Clear vision and integrated strategy, Existence of strong motive (burning platform), Availability of financial resources, Level of knowledge and experience, Organization culture, The role of consultant, Benchmarking and sharing best practices
33	Clegg et al.	2010	Critical success factor statements for quality management are agreed with, although not all are implemented well. The findings also show that many quality tools are not known or understood well; and that training has an important role in raising their awareness and making sure they are used correctly.
34	Praveen Goyal Zillur Rahman Absar Ahmad Kazmi	2015	A total twelve important practices were identified with the help of a literature review and expert opinions. The relative importance of the different practice on different dimensions of corporate sustainability was identified by using the AHP technique. With the help of experts, major corporate sustainability practices for a manufacturing sector were identified.
35	Khanna et al	2011	CSF: Top management commitment, Role of quality department, Process quality management, Product/service design, Education and training, Supplier quality management, Customer satisfaction, Employee empowerment and involvement, Business/quality results, Information and analysis, Benchmarking, Quality citizenship, Quality culture
36	Yadav and Desai	2016	Barriers: Lack of top management attitude, commitment and involvement, Lack of training and education, Poor project selection and prioritization, Lack of resources (financial, technical, human, etc.), Weak link between the CI projects and the strategic objectives of the Organization, Resistance of culture change, Poor communication, Lack of leadership skills and visionary and supportive leadership, Lack of consideration of the human factors, Lack of awareness of the benefits of Lean/Six Sigma, Wrong selection of Lean/Six Sigma tools, Narrow view of LSS as a set of tools, techniques and practices, Lack of understanding of the different types of customers / VOC, Lack of employee engagement and participation/lack of team autonomy, Lack of process thinking and process ownership, , High implementation cost, Lack of experience in Lean/ Six Sigma project implementation, Lack of awareness of the need for Lean/Six Sigma, Ineffective project management, Poor selection of

Sr. No.	Authors	Year	Main Findings & Critical Success Factors
			<p>candidates for belts training, Lack of clear vision and a future, Lack of an effective model or roadmap to guide the implementation, Time consuming, Lack of estimation of implementation cost, Weak infrastructure, Replicating another organization's Lean/Six Sigma strategy, Lack of a performance measurement system, Lack of application of statistical theory, Weak linking to suppliers, Misalignment between the project aim, the main goals of the company and the customer demand.</p>
37	Faisal Talib Zillur Rahman	2015	<p>The synthesized results have highlighted that the barrier 'lack of communication' is the most significant among all the other barriers. It is followed by 'lack of top-management commitment', 'employee's resistance to change', and 'lack of coordination between departments'. The least significant barrier is found to be 'high turnover at management level'.</p> <p>Barriers: Attitude of employees towards quality, Employee's resistance to change, High turnover at management level, Human resource barrier, Inadequate use of empowerment and teamwork, Lack of communication, Lack of continuous improvement culture, Lack of coordination between department, Lack of proper training and education, Lack of top-management commitment, No benchmarking, Poor planning</p>
38	Garcia et al.	2014	<p>Management commitment and Education and training are the basis or pillar for a successful kaizen implementation program and that its performance can be measured by best process, workers and customer satisfaction.</p> <p>CSF: Commitment and motivation of staff, Support from senior management, Allocated resources (time, economic, spaces), Leadership, Developing a culture of continuous improvement, Set goals for improvement programs, Using an appropriate methodology, Standardization and process measurement, Organization of support teams, Presence of a facilitator to support the program, Interdepartmental communication, Differences between the focus of improvement and the existing culture, Employee attitude, Interdepartmental cooperation, Follow the PDCA cycle, Training and education, Heterogeneity of improvement teams, Assessment system, Skills and experience, Establish policies, objectives and structure, Clarify goals and common ideas</p>
39	McNamara	2014	<p>Research has found that human beings are limited in their ability to process information (Simon, 1976). For instance, investors often fall prey to herding behavior and decide based on what others have chosen. They are fooled by randomness and underestimate its impact on their financial decisions (Shiller, 1984; Olsen, 1996). Likewise, management in all its forms should be made aware of cognitive biases and their effects on decision making; hence, relevant psychology training programs need to be created. All individuals who make decisions in an organization are subject to biases; therefore, management and those who make the most important decisions should be especially aware of the different types of biases that affect their own personal decision making capabilities.</p>
40	Andre Luís Helleno, Aroldo José Isaias de Moraes, Alexandre Tadeu Simon		<p>The conceptual method brings a new group of indicators associated with economic, social and environmental dimensions, which, together with the traditional indicators of VSM (Lean KPIs), seek to assess manufacturing processes and thus generate actions of continuous improvement (Kaizen) to develop sustainable manufacturing processes. The application of VSM identified the need for increased efforts in collecting data in relation to the traditional VSM. This is because information related to the economic, social</p>

Sr. No.	Authors	Year	Main Findings & Critical Success Factors
			and environmental dimensions are not monitored in the manufacturing process but rather by other departments, such as accounting, human resources, work safety and environmental management.
41	Antosz and Stadnicka	2017	The results show that many of SME are ready to implement Lean Manufacturing philosophy. These companies want to improve their operation or they realize the need of waste elimination. The major wastes are: waiting for material (49%), unnecessary movements (41%) and machine failures (39%). The key reasons for implementing LM are: the intention to improve the company's operation (81%) and the need to gain a competitive advantage (50%). However, still many of the companies (55%) do not implement the LM philosophy whereas the companies which have implemented the LM philosophy use mostly 5S method (29%).
42	Bin Zhou	2012	Results demonstrate that most of the firms have a relatively good understanding of lean concept and philosophy. Majority of the firms regard lean as costs savings, continuous improvement, and waste reduction. It was also found that the main driving factors that encourage SMEs to implement lean are: cost reduction, improve profit margin, reduce inventory and assets required, improve utilization of plant/facility, and maintain competitive position.
43	Jain and Malik	2013	This paper presents a review of lean manufacturing adopted by manufacturing organizations. It has been established beyond doubt that to remain in business it has now become the necessity for all the industries especially Indian SME's to adopt the tools of lean principles. Indian small scale industries have to shed off their conservative attitude and should reform their working practices with lean tools. Attitude of work force in these industries also requires a lot of cultural change to save their livelihood.
44	Panwar et al.	2015	It is observed that the level of implementation of lean manufacturing in Indian process industries is still low. Results indicate that Indian process industries those who have implemented lean found lean to be very useful to reduce wastes and to increase quality. Major lean practices being implemented by Indian process industries are primarily those which are related to waste elimination or improvement in quality. Indian process industries found that important challenges to implement lean are to produce in small batches, to arrange for lean experts and to impart training to employees.
45	Ravikumar et al.	2016	The SEM enhances its significant use with the perfect interrelationship between the performance factors though they are found to be only significant in the interaction between the criteria. The ranking obtained from TOPSIS and fuzzy TOPSIS is useful for the industries to pay their attention on some important issues while achieving the prescribed targets.
46	Panizzolo et al.	2012	Six areas for assessment of lean Manufacturing implementation have been discussed to identify operational benefits gained by organizations: Process and equipment, Manufacturing planning and control, Human resources, Product design, Supplier relationships
47	Sharma et al.	2016	Through extensive literature review and discussions with industry practitioners, this research identified 8 criteria for lean implementation at a brainstorming session of experts from automobile and machine tool sector. These include 5S, VSM, JIT, SMED, CIM, CE, training and ERP. ISM methodology is used to develop the structural model by creating SSIM, reachability matrix, level partitioning, and finally formulation of the model. MICMAC analysis is employed to establish the driving power and dependence

Sr. No.	Authors	Year	Main Findings & Critical Success Factors
			powers of the 8 identified lean implementation criteria.
48	Dibia et al.	2014	The LPPO model is a Lean implementation model that is flexible and easily adaptable. It is system based, people driven, customer centered, with measurable outcome and a drive for continuous improvement.
49	Dombrowski and Mielke	2014	In this paper, the attributes of a true CIP were described and some basic lean leadership approaches were explained. Based on these approaches, 15 practice-oriented requirements were identified, that could be derived from study results and various references regarding advices, error reports and deficits in leadership during lean implementations. These new requirements were framed as rules for lean leaders to support their daily efforts toward a true continuous improvement.
50	Alefari et al.	2017	In the present paper, the importance of top management and leadership in the introduction and implementation of lean manufacturing has been discussed. Based on a survey undertaken within the UK manufacturing sector, top management has been highlighted as the key success factor, particularly for SMEs. A number of expectations from the management were discussed such as the top management commitment, the selection of the appropriate leadership style, the engagement and development of capable lean employees.
51	Worley and Doolen	2015	The effects of Organization structure and employee problem solving skills has been discussed in detail that how does it influence Lean Manufacturing implementation and its successful continuation.

3. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

After going through comprehensive literature study it has been clear that Lean Manufacturing principles are significantly important for the industries desire to improve operational and financial performance by eliminating non value added activities (NVA) and wastes. It has been prominent to adopt the Lean tools to make the organizations viable efficiently for longer time in the market. It has now become the inevitable for all the industries especially Indian manufacturing SMEs to adopt the tools of lean principles. Indian SMEs have to leave conservative attitude and should reform their operation practices with lean tools. Attitude of work force in these industries also requires a lot of cultural change to save their livelihood (Jain and Malik, 2013). Although many organizations try to implement the Lean Manufacturing tools only few of them have completely understand the process and have prepare framework accordingly to execute the Lean Manufacturing practices. It is essential for organizations to assimilate entire concept of Lean Manufacturing which are willing to implement it in order to successfully achieve the potential benefits of the philosophy. Firms should give equal importance in consideration of critical success factors (CSF), because if the CSF are considered appropriately it will ensure success and sustainability of Lean Manufacturing practice. Research have also suggested that top management commitment and support, Organizational culture and Leadership style are the profound factors in achieving

success with Lean. To succeed with a lean program in a factory, top management commitment and involvement is important. Dynamic and persuasive leadership must be sustained throughout the process progress. In order to evolve continuously organization should arrange education and knowledge development program relentlessly. The cross functional ability of the team member can be the asset for the firm to support internal manufacturing operations and other operations as well. It also ensure quick return on investment for the projects as team members are well aware of competition forces and market dynamics. The study suggests that leadership is the most crucial factor for lean implementation success and availability of adequate training, acts as a catalyst (Patri and Suresh, 2013). Results from the study show that the problem lies primarily with an aging and high seniority hourly workforce and a lack of committed leadership at this research site (Sim and Rogers, 2008). Within the UK manufacturing sector, top management has been highlighted as the key success factor, particularly for SMEs. A number of expectations from the management were discussed such as the top management commitment, the selection of the appropriate leadership style, the engagement and development of capable lean employees (Alefari et al., 2017). On the other hand factors such as financial capabilities, Employee training and knowledge, Organizational readiness, Communication, Employee involvement and engagement, Cross functional team development to name a few should be considered carefully as well. The results show that many of SME are

ready to implement Lean Manufacturing philosophy and desire to increase their activities or they identify the need of waste elimination. The major wastes are: waiting for material (49%), unnecessary movements (41%) and machine failures (39%). The key reasons for implementing LM are: the intention to improve the company's operation (81%) and the need to gain a competitive advantage (50%). However, still many of the companies (55%) do not implement the LM philosophy whereas company mostly use 5S method (29%) (Antosz and Stadnicka, 2017).

4. CONCLUSION

It has been clear that Lean Manufacturing principles are significantly important for the industries desire to improve operational and financial performance by eliminating non value added activities (NVA) and wastes. Through the comprehensive literature review it has been clear that very few attempt has been made to identify the critical success factors (CSF) for successful and sustain implementation of Lean Manufacturing philosophy in the manufacturing SMEs in India and global as well. Study has also suggested that organization willing to attempt implement Lean Methodology should carefully consider critical success factors and carefully evaluate organizational capabilities to allocate the available resources in the most effective and efficient manner. Most important barriers to overcome are: Top management related barriers, poor belief on the approach/ advantage, change inertia, top management commitment lasted too shortly, financial barriers, Timing to set realistic timescales for change and to make effective use of commitments. Organization should also consider inter-relation between the critical success factors (CSF) to identify their effects on the entire methodology to successfully attempt Lean Manufacturing practices.

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